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Recruitment System and Selection of Placement of Educators in the Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar

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Abstract

The recruitment and placement system for teaching staff is one of the most important elements in improving the quality of education. Educators are members of the community who are devoted and appointed to support the implementation of education. Includes education unit managers, overseers, study tutors, supervisors, researchers, developers, librarians, laboratory assistants and learning resource technicians. One of the problems that often occur in the recruitment and placement of teaching staff is that the planning of recruitment is less mature so that there is often a failure in achieving school goals because a lot of work that should be done by some people must be done alone. Based on this problem, research was carried out recruitment and selection systems, placement of educators at the Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School in Makassar. Using pure qualitative research methods. The data collection techniques, through observation and interviews. Data analysis methods are used triangulation so that data becomes more accurate.

Recruitment of educators at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School is based on preparation and planning. The system used sequentially starts from the dissemination of information about job vacancies for the recruitment of teachers, acceptance of application files, and file selection. Furthermore, the placement of employees who are declared as graduated is based on their respective competencies and skills with an open, free, objective principle without discrimination. Placement in a position that is in accordance with the expertise, skills, talents, and abilities, while remaining in accordance with the prevailing laws and regulations.

Keywords: Recruitment, Selection, Placement of Educators

Introduction

School is an educational institution or institution which is a means to carry out the educational process. Schools are not only used as a gathering place between teachers and students but rather a complex and dynamic system. In addition, schools are a place to create educated human beings in accordance with the vision, mission and planned targets.

Management is needed so that the management of education in schools is directed through the development of clear vision, mission, and goals. It could be a school that has qualified teachers, adequate facilities and infrastructure, students whose quality is above average but fails to realize quality graduates. This could be due to the lack of clear vision, mission, and goals, in addition to the lack of coordination of the work team with the school management.

Educators are one of the most important elements in improving the quality of education. Education personnel is members of the community who are devoted and appointed to support the implementation of education, which includes education unit managers, overseers, study tutors, supervisors, researchers, developers, librarians, laboratory assistants and learning resource technicians. Educators are educators who qualified as teachers, counselors, tutors, lecturers, tutors, instructors, facilitators, and other terms in accordance with their specialization, as well as participating in education (Suparlan, 2006).

Seeing the role of educators and education staff is so important, it is necessary to have a recruitment strategy that can produce professional educators. Educator recruitment is a set of activities and processes used to obtain a number of qualified people at the right place and time in accordance with applicable legal provisions so that people and schools can select each other based on their best interests in the long term and short term. (Training and Education Guide, 2008)

The quality of human resources of an organization is initially determined by the quality of prospective workers or applicants. Starting from recruitment, which is a process to find and attract applicants who are capable of working for an organization. This process begins when the organization seeks new prospective workers, from various sources and various ways, and ends when the job application is submitted (Marwansyah, 2010: 106). If recruitment is well taken, the results will be good. (Sondang P. Siagian, 2008).

Islam encourages its followers to choose prospective employees based on their knowledge, experience and technical capabilities. Good employees are Muslim individuals who have high motivation abilities. In the development of the quality of human resources (employees) is to realize two basic traits namely strong and trustworthy (trustworthy). This is in accordance with the word of God Almighty. In Surah al-Qasas / 28: 26

قَالَتْ إِحْدَاهُمَا يَا أَبَتِ اسْتَجِرْهُ إِنَّ خَيْرَ مَنِ اسْتَجَرْتَ الْقَوِيُّ الْأَمِينُ ﴿٢٦﴾

"One of the two women said": O my Father take it as people who work (on us), because actually the most whether you take to work (for us) is a strong person who can be trusted again" (Kementerian Agama RI, 2012).

The paragraph explained that strength also requires the fulfillment of skills in science, workers must be good at work, know their nature, demands and be able to carry out the tasks for which they are responsible. In addition, workers must also be trustworthy or trustworthy. Trust is a demand in every job, because trust means to be sincere and feel in the supervision of God when carrying out any work. On the other hand, that the fulfillment of the elements of the mandate of the labor force in particular and mankind in general is a factor that will prevent damage in all forms, and the impact on the wastage of

economic resources, weaknesses and supervision in carrying out the work, rampant bribery, and the confiscation of the people Muslim.

The above verse, Allah swt. provide an explanation that a good worker is a strong and trustworthy person. In the interpretation of al-Misbah, it is explained that the strength in question is strength in various fields. Therefore, it must first be seen what fields will be assigned to selected applicants. Furthermore, the trust in question is personal integrity, which demands trust in nature so that it does not feel that what is in its grasp is private property, but the mandate that must be maintained and if asked to return, it must be willing to return it. (M. Quraish Shihab, 2002)

The purpose of good recruitment is to get educators and educators who are in accordance with the specified qualifications. The continuity of school activities in the element of human resource competency is a very important element. The running of the school program is very much determined by the people involved. Buildings with facilities, equipment, work tools, methods, and community support are not enough, if the people in it are less competent, it will be very difficult to achieve the expected educational goals.

One of the problems that often occur in the recruitment of teaching staff is the problem of less mature recruitment planning so that there are often failures in achieving school objectives because many of the work that should be done by several people must be done alone. This usually occurs because of the lack of experts in certain fields of work. Sometimes there is also a mismatch between staff assignments to their duties and functions, for example placing a math teacher based solely on the applicant's talent rather than on the applicant's educational background without being supported by training. Even the problem does not stop here, given the role of educators and education staff is the main implementer of educational activities in schools. It is not uncommon to find teachers who lack passion in doing their work, which results in less successful goals achieved. This is caused by many factors, one of which is the lack of motivation of the teacher so that in doing his work does not provide maximum performance.

Recruitment System for Teaching Staff

In carrying out the system of recruitment of well-trained educators planning, it is very necessary for every activity that will be carried out. Expecting that the activities we are going to carry out can run smoothly and can achieve goals without good planning. Planning is a preparation step in carrying out a job to achieve certain goals. The process of drafting a plan that must be considered is preparing everything needed to achieve the goal, namely by collecting data, recording and analyzing data, and formulating decisions.

Then pay attention to the principles of recruitment that must be held firmly in the planning or implementation of teacher recruitment, including: (Ibrahim Bafadal: 2008)

1. Teacher recruitment must be carefully designed to meet needs.
2. Teacher recruitment must be done objectively. This means that the new employee selection committee determines that applicants who pass and applicants who do not pass objectively. Applicants who do not meet the requirements objectively are judged not to pass, and vice versa applicants who meet the requirements are determined as applicants who pass.

3. In order to obtain a candidate professional, the selection of new employees should be comprehensive including all aspects of the requirements that must be possessed by prospective teachers.

Educator Placement Method

The principle that needs to be done in terms of placement of educators is "The Right Man and The Right Job". This is intended to make the placement of educators to be effective and the implementation of work can achieve satisfactory results. The placement of the right educator will produce the ability to carry out the task well, the level of creativity, high initiative, responsibility and sense of belonging to the work.

The placement of educators is to place someone in a job that is in accordance with their skills and knowledge in school. Placement of an educator is an activity carried out by the manager to place someone educator in the work and position in the organization.

Placement of educators is the process of assigning tasks and work to educators who pass the selection to be carried out in accordance with the predetermined scope, as well as being able to account for all the risks and possibilities that occur on the duties and work, authority, and responsibilities.

The factors that are considered in the placement of educators are:

1. Education as the main requirement
2. Work knowledge Job
3. skills that include physical skills, skills, mental and social skills
4. Work experience.

System Recruitment of Teachers in Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar

1. Recruitment Planning Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar

Before recruitment implemented then the Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar planning, things to do is the job analysis and job analysis. Both of these analyzes are carried out to obtain data regarding what formations are empty. How many employees are needed, and to determine the minimum requirements needed by prospective employees. In the implementation of this job analysis, the Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar gave a mandate to the head of the madrasah to report if there was a shortage of staff. After the reports from each madrasa were collected, the chairman of the Darul Hikmah Islamic Junior High School foundation recommended to the personnel department to form a recruitment committee implementation committee.

Based on the results of the interview with the head of the Islamic Middle School Darul Hikmah Makassar foundation, the recruitment and selection of educators were entirely handed over to the school while still conforming to the foundation. The recruitment of new teaching staff is usually carried out at the beginning of each school year.

2. Recruitment Methods and Techniques of Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar

Based on the results of an interview with Mrs. Dra. Wangisa, S.Pd., MM, Head of Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School, the preparations made in carrying out the recruitment and selection of educators in this institution are carried out by analyzing the level of needs, including analyzing any vacant positions, the number of vacant positions, increase in the number of students, mutation of employees (due to change of duty, illness or death), determination of department specifications and determining requirements that must be met by applicants. Still Based on the results of interviews with the head of the Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School the recruitment process stage was the first to open vacancies conducted by publishing through posting information in school making, newspapers and foundation notice boards. This was done with the aim of being able to be read by students, as well as the community so many were aware of the existence of teacher vacancies at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School. The results of an interview with one of the Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School students that there was indeed an announcement was made about the shortage of educators in school making and newspapers. The opening of vacancies is carried out for 17 days with the aim of attracting the attention of prospective applicants so that later they will get many applicants. At the time of their application, the applicants submit the file to the foundation, the applicants must fill out a registration form and submit the files in the form of a copy of diplomas SI, curriculum vitae, bio applicants, a copy of certificate toefl, copy of ID card. After the announcement of new teaching staff vacancies has spread, many people know that there are job openings at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Junior High School, as stated in the announcement of new teaching staff vacancies. So many people are interested in and enter job applications. The committee starts to carry out activities which include: Serving people who enter job applications.

This job application is usually received directly by the security guard on duty in front of the gate of Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School, then the security guard gives the applications to the recruitment committee. This has been the rule of the parties at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School, that whatever enters the Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School will be received directly by the security guard first. After the application is submitted, the committee checks all the items that must be included with the application letter. After all entry applications are then continued with the recapitulation of all applicants in the applicant's recapitulation format. It aims to facilitate the selection process and notification of announcements or call the next stage of selection. To obtain educators who are really right for school, the recruitment committee is responsible for determining the candidates to be chosen. In order for recruitment to be effective, it must know what educators are needed. The recruitment process of educators at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Junior High School is still carried out in a naturalistic manner, namely, the school is proposing the addition of teaching staff to the foundation. The recruitment process is handled by the foundation which is then handed over to the school to be selected. Selection of prospective educators is selected by schools involving school principals, curriculum officers, and subject teachers.

3. The principle of recruiting educators from Darul Hikmah Islamic Junior High School Makassar

Based on the results of interviews conducted with the principal Dra. Wangisa, S.Pd., MM, He said that the principles of the recruitment of educators and education staff had been carried out based on the existing provisions. That all prospective educators who will be recruited must be based on existing needs, carried out objectively without discriminating and carried out professionally with full responsibility.

Based on the information I got through an interview with one of the teachers at Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School, he said that basically, the principles of recruitment implementation are in accordance with the existing principles, namely: the principle of justice, objective, and professional and in accordance with existing needs.

This is in line with the deputy headmaster of the Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar saying that the Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar has conducted a recruitment system in accordance with its principles ranging from justice, professional, objective and in accordance with the needs of this school. Based on the results of the above research, it can be concluded that Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School has conducted a recruitment system in accordance with the principles of recruitment argues, Ibrahim Bafadal Namely: according to needs, objective and professional.

Educator Placement System at Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar

Based on interviews with the principal of Darul Hikmah Makassar Islamic Middle School Dra. Wangisa, S.Pd., MM, He said that the principles of the placement of teaching staff have been carried out properly. Where every new educator is placed, it is based on their respective skills or skills so that they can work effectively and efficiently.

In line with the deputy principal of the Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar, he said that the Principles of Placement of educators were carried out based on open principles. Free, objective, and fair, and equal without discrimination. The placement of educators is directed to place educators in positions that are in accordance with the skills, talents, interests, and abilities with regard to dignity, human rights and legal protection.

The placement of educators is carried out by observing several F factors. As an interview with the principal of the Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School in Makassar Dra. Wangisa, S.Pd., MM, He said that the factors that are considered in the placement of educators are education that is in accordance with the needs in school this, experience work, knowledge, and physical, mental and health conditions of educators.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion in the above research, it can be concluded that the Recruitment System for Educators at Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School in Makassar. Planning and preparation of teacher recruitment, Dissemination of

announcements for the acceptance of new teaching staff, Acceptance of new teaching staff applications, Selection of applicants.

The placement system of Educator Personnel at Darul Hikmah Islamic Middle School Makassar implements several principles for the placement of educator staff based on an open, free, objective and fair principle, and equal without discrimination. The placement of educators is directed to place educators in positions that are in accordance with the skills, talents, interests, and abilities with regard to dignity, human rights and legal protection.

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